

TECHNICAL SCIENCES

RECOMMENDATIONS ON DESIGNING THE STRUCTURE OF REPAIR AND RECOVERY BODIES WHILE MANAGING TECHNICAL CONDITION OF MILITARY EQUIPMENT DURING COMBAT OPERATIONS

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Abstract.

The article is prepared on a topical issue related to improving the quality of maintenance and recovery of military equipment process management in the conditions of carrying out combat operations (CO). In order to improve the quality of management of military equipment (ME) technical condition (TC), relevant recommendations are suggested regarding the design of repair and recovery bodies (RRB) structure while managing ME TC in the conditions of carrying out combat operations.

Keywords: combat operations; military equipment; technical condition; maintenance, repair and recovery body.

1. INTRODUCTION.

Today, in the conditions of the large-scale invasion of the Russian Federation on the territory of Ukraine, the Armed Forces of Ukraine faced a serious problem in maintaining the necessary level of ME combat capability and extending the terms of its operation, since a significant part of it has exhausted the performance potential [1; 2]. Under the conditions of carrying out combat operations intensively, when there may be a mass failure of ME as a result of combat damage or critical operational conditions, the appropriate efforts to maintain the combat capability of ME increase significantly.

Formulation of the problem. On the basis of the proposed scientific and methodological apparatus for the management of ME TC in the conditions of carrying out CO [3] and the studies that have been conducted concerning the effectiveness of management of ME technical condition under these circumstances, practical recommendations have been developed to increase the efficiency of RRB in the conditions of conducting CO.

Analysis of recent research and publications.

While searching for scientific publications in this subject area, one cannot ignore the scientific works of well-known scientists such as O. Vorobiov [4], B. Demyanchuk [5], V. Sivak [6] and others, who consider sufficiently effective approaches to the management of ME TC.

The purpose of the article. Development of recommendations for the design of the RRB structure while managing ME TC with the help of an improved methodology for determining and adjusting the periodicity of ME maintenance.

2. RESEARCH RESULTS.

The conducted analysis of research and publications in this subject area gives grounds for asserting that the improvement of the quality of ME TC management is achieved by maintaining the required number of serviceable ME, the time of their intended use and their timely recovery in the conditions of CO. At the same time, the main functional component for performing the tasks defined above will be repair and recovery bodies. However, neither availability nor well-founded compo-

sition of RRB do not guarantee their effective use as intended and the practical employment of improved methods of determining and adjusting the optimal frequency of ME maintenance in the conditions of carrying out CO.

Based on the mentioned above, depending on the conditions of carrying out CO, the number of ME samples that require maintenance, and if necessary, their recovery, for each specific case it is proposed to conduct a substantiation (design) of a rational composition and equipment of the corresponding RRB.

The degree of readiness of RRB to perform tasks should be close to, and sometimes even exceed, the degree of readiness of combat units. In addition, it should be taken into account that in connection with the saturation of troops with structurally complex and high-performance military equipment, the increase in requirements for the performance of assigned tasks, the mutual ties between individual RRBs have rapidly increased and deepened. Based on this fact, it is suggested to develop recommendations for designing both temporarily created and stationary RRBs.

Taking into account the general requirements concerning RRB, it is necessary to determine the main stages of their development, which would be universal and correspond to the various conditions of ME employment when using for its intended purpose.

For this purpose, it is necessary to justify the necessity to create RRB, as well as to develop documentation for the creation of each of them. To develop this recommendation, we should proceed from the following general requirements put forward to RRB, namely: ensuring

that troops (forces) perform assigned tasks by maintaining military equipment in a serviceable (operable) condition and its timely recovery (repair); performing recovery works in field conditions within minimal time limits, efforts and resources; equipping with high-performance, modern universal equipment that meets the conditions of its employment; constant readiness to perform functional tasks in accordance with their purpose; the possibility of echeloning while maintaining technological independence; the ability to perform the functional tasks under any conditions of the environment and time (with minimal non-productive expenses); availability of means of communication and control appropriate to the tactics of application, functional purpose and place in the operational construction of troops.

In addition to the abovementioned requirements, it should be taken into account that the development of the repair body is carried out on the basis of the technical task [7; 8]. At the same time, technical suggestions, technical project, drawings and other documentation are being developed.

The development of the technical task is preceded by the definition (development) of the tactical and technical requirements for the development of the repair body or system as a whole.

The development of the system (repair body) can also envisage solving various tasks. Depending on the availability of initial information and set goals, development tasks by type are shown in the table. 1.

The content of the tasks listed in the table. 1 depends on what is meant by "initial object", "system" and "final object".

Table 1

Type of tasks	Initial object (resources)	System (process)	Final object
1.	given	given	must be found
2.	given	must be found	must be found
3.	given	must be found	given
4.	must be found	given	given
5.	must be found	must be found	given
6.	must be found	given	must be found

If, for example, it is understood that: "initial object" is ME characterized by certain indicators; "system" is a set of repair means of RRB, characterized by structural, functional and other indicators; the "final object" is the technical readiness of ME, then the development tasks can be formulated as follows.

The task of the 1st type: according to the given values of the indicators (aggregate of ME, its failure, labour and time expenses for recovery, capabilities of RRB that create a system), it is necessary to determine at what level (compared to the initial) the technical readiness of ME in the required moment of time will be.

The task of the 2nd type: according to the given values of the indicators, to determine the structural construction of the system and its elements, the appliances for servicing the given "input" and technical readiness of the ME in the required moments of time.

The task of the 3rd type: according to the given values of the indicators, to determine what structure and functional properties the system and individual repair

means should be characterized by, that will ensure the necessary technical readiness of the ME.

The task of the 4th type: according to the given values of the indicators of the system and individual repair means, the value of the technical readiness of ME at the necessary moments of time, to determine for which aggregate of ME, the intensity of its failure and the types of repair, this system will be more adapted. That is, what repair fund must be sent to this system so that the products of the system meet the specified requirements.

The most common is the task of the 5th type. Its purpose is to determine the "input" parameters and find the optimal structure and other properties of the system as a whole and its elements based on a given indicator of the necessary technical readiness of ME.

To solve this task, the following initial information is required: ME failure; expenditure of resources on recovery of ME; products provided by the system; restrictions imposed on the decisions made during the development of the system and its elements.

The task of the 6th type is a variation of the 1st and 4th tasks.

System development can be considered as a process consisting of operations (stages) that are diverse in terms of content and goals. This process consists in processing information in order to create new functions and connections. According to the methods used in solving tasks, system development is divided into synthesis, analysis and selection, that is, the stages of obtaining a preliminary decision, checking and choosing the best option.

The content and sequence of system development stages depends on the type of task and the depth of its processing. The task of the 5th type has as its goal finding the initial object (input) and the properties of the system for a given final object (output). The stages of the process of solving such a task will be: determination of the functional tasks of the system and its elements to ensure the given level of technical readiness of ME at a certain point in time; determination of parameters of the flow of ME failures and requirements for its recovery; determination of the properties (indicators) of the unit requirement for repair; determination of the parameters of the flow of requirements sent to the system and its elements, and searching for the general structure of this system; development of structurally effective single RRB for each level of the system; development of production sites and selection of RRB technological equipment; development of staff, tables of stores and equipment, technological documentation, etc.; simulation of the RRB (system) functioning process and choosing the best (optimal) option; creation of an experimental model of the RRB (system), conducting an experiment and making a decision regarding the structure, equipment, capabilities and conditions of operation of a single RRB and the system as a whole.

The suggested stages of development of repair bodies to increase the efficiency of the process of ME recovery can be used in the conditions of carrying out CO and during the organization of the process of ME recovery in challenging conditions (liquidation of consequences of emergency situations, operation of ME in difficult climatic conditions as part of peacekeeping missions, etc.), as well as to accomplish tasks during command post exercises and ensure the educational process.

3. CONCLUSIONS AND PROSPECTS OF FURTHER RESEARCH.

Thus, recommendations have been developed for the design of the RRB structure while managing ME TC, which can be used in the conditions of carrying out combat operations and during the organization of the process of equipment recovery in challenging conditions (liquidation of the consequences of emergency

situations, operation of ME in challenging climatic conditions as part of peacekeeping missions, etc.), as well as for accomplishing tasks during command post exercises and ensuring the educational process. Their implementation will allow to synthesize a new structure of RRB individually for each case of their application, depending on the type of CO and the situation in which ME is used for its intended purpose, which in totality will ensure the rational implementation of the developed methodology [3] into practical activity.

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